
DECREES ON MEASURES TO FURTHER IMPROVE THE SYSTEM OF EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract.

However, the term "inclusive teaching" has been introduced for twenty years, the practical implementing are not working properly. This could be because the population of the Uzbekistan Republic are not aware of what this term means and what this term can provide. In order to make this type of teaching more effective and common, new laws have already been announced by the government. This article focuses on some of the decrees and explain it in an ordinary way.

Key words.

Inclusive teaching, disability, school, teaching, laws.

Introduction

Despite the fact that Uzbekistan has 20 years of experience in promoting inclusive education, 20 years ago Uzbekistan did not have the status of a legal pedagogical experiment, and now inclusive education is officially an educational model. was accepted as form of the education system. This we can conclude that if one's child has special educational needs, they can send him to any local kindergarten and any school, and the educational institution - in theory - will teach the child there. Moreover, the school must create conditions for their needs. Uzbekistan is still at the beginning of the process of implementing inclusive education. According to statistics, following facts can be introduced.

1. About 40% of the total population of Uzbekistan (32.6 million), are school aged children up to the age of 16.
2. However, only 82,000 of children in Uzbekistan⁶ are legally recognized as having a disability which represent 0.85% of the school aged population.
3. In 2015, 30,257 children with disabilities attended mainstream schools.
4. However, 7,399 school-aged children registered with disabilities were outside of the formal education system.

5. 17,9608 children studied in schools and boarding schools for special education. Of these children, 14,636 were in special boarding schools, and 3,324 were in special schools.

6. Only 6,600 children had the legal status of disabled children, and at the same time 9,638 children were enrolled in home based schooling delivered by teachers of regular schools

Methodology

In order to achieve the goal of this article, over 10 articles which are related to the topic have been investigated. The researcher adopts descriptive and empirical analytical approaches as far as data collection and discussion are concerned. Moreover, in order to compare academic writing and text language, the comparative method is utilized.

Results and discussions

On October 12, the Cabinet of Ministers approved a number of legal documents on the development of inclusive education for children with special educational needs. The document was developed in accordance with the President's decision of October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs". The concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2025 includes the development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan, improvement of the education system for children with special educational needs, and educational services provided to them. implies the following main priority tasks for quality improvement:

- developing and approving requirements for the buildings of educational institutions attended by children with special educational needs;
- implementation of measures aimed at providing these educational institutions with the necessary literature, educational tools, material and technical base and equipment for training in various professions;
- organization of an inclusive education system, provision of educational institutions with special equipment (lifting devices, ramps, fences, etc.), as well as with appropriate personnel (special teachers, psychological and pedagogical supervision of children experts in making);
- gradual provision of boarding schools with special equipment for adaptation and integration of children with special educational needs, etc.

The decision approved the regulation on inclusive education of children with special needs in general educational institutions. It implies the following:

- goals and tasks of inclusive education;
- the procedure for organizing inclusive education and elementary remedial classes in schools and the educational process for children with special education needs;
- the procedure for admitting children to inclusive education and primary remedial classes;
- measures to control and manage the quality of education in inclusive education and primary remedial classes.

Besides:

- specialized educational institutions for children with physical, mental, emotional or intellectual disabilities;
- sanatorium-resort-type specialized educational state institutions;
- the regulation on the procedure for individual home education for children with physical, mental, sensory or intellectual disabilities, as well as children who need long-term treatment, was also approved.

Besides that the decree approved the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System in 2020-2025, as well as the Roadmap for its implementation. In accordance with the decree, in the 2021/2022 academic year:

- the system of inclusive education is being introduced in one of the secondary schools in the cities, as well as districts of Tashkent;
- basic remedial classes for children with special educational needs are opening in one of the secondary schools of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent;
- specialized groups are being created in one of the vocational schools of Kashkadarya, Fergana and Khorezm regions for the graduates of specialized educational institutions and children with special educational needs.

From the 2021/2022 academic year, 11-year compulsory general secondary-education will be provided in specialized educational institutions (in auxiliary and boarding schools for children with intellectual development disabilities – 9 years). In addition, vocational training courses are organized for students in grades 10-11 (in auxiliary and boarding schools for children with intellectual disabilities – grades 8-9) of specialized educational institutions. Starting from January 1, 2021, management staff of specialized educational institutions will receive a monthly bonus for special working conditions in the amount of 100 percent of their base wage rate. It is also planned to establish a Laboratory of Inclusive Education at the

Republican Center for Vocational Guidance and Psychological-Pedagogical Diagnosis of Students. One of the main tasks of this laboratory is to create conditions for inclusive education in secondary schools, to develop criteria for determining the quality and effectiveness of inclusive education and to monitor their implementation¹²².

Conclusion

Particular attention has to be paid to the importance of early childhood development (including early identification and early intervention), inclusive pre-school learning opportunities, improving health and reducing poverty. Education system reform must be based on a twin track approach which seeks to strengthen the education system through inclusive education: improving quality whilst ensuring that marginalized children are fully included. This will involve recruitment, training and support for early intervention service professionals, pre-school teachers and basic education teachers so that they are equipped to plan for and meet the educational and social needs of diverse groups of learners. Specialized services and resources will always have an important role, but they must be designed and enabled to support teachers and the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream non-segregator settings through the implementation of universal inclusive rights-based principles.

THE LIST OF THE USED LITERATURE:

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4. Tilavova, M. (2021). The Impact of Motivation In Learning Foreign Languages. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).

¹²²<https://kun.uz/en/news/2020/10/14/uzbek-schools-to-introduce-inclusive-education>

5. Uzoqova Xayriniso (2023) Opportunities of internet in teaching english in the classroom, International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers

INTERNET RESOURCES:

1. <https://kun.uz/en/news/2020/10/14/uzbek-schools-to-introduce-inclusive-education>
2. <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/3566/file/inclusive%20policy%20brief%20eng>